

Original Research

Compensation and Career Development as Drivers of Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

This study examines how compensation and career development influence employee performance through job satisfaction within a highly regulated professional service context. Drawing on human resource management and motivational perspectives, the research investigates the direct effects of compensation and career development on employee performance, as well as their indirect effects through job satisfaction. Extending prior studies that largely assume compensation as a direct performance driver, this study emphasizes job satisfaction as a central explanatory mechanism, particularly in state-owned professional service organizations. Data were collected from 134 active employees of PT Sucofindo (Persero) Banjarmasin Branch using a census approach and analyzed through variance-based structural equation modeling. The results indicate that compensation does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance, despite showing a positive relationship. Career development demonstrates a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Both compensation and career development significantly enhance job satisfaction, which in turn positively affects employee performance. Further analysis confirms that job satisfaction fully mediates the compensation–performance relationship and partially mediates the career development–performance relationship. The model explains a substantial proportion of variance in employee performance. These findings contribute theoretically by clarifying the conditional role of compensation and highlighting job satisfaction as a key mechanism linking human resource practices to performance in regulated public service settings. Practical implications are offered for state-owned organizations seeking to improve performance through integrated compensation, career development, and job satisfaction strategies.

Keywords: Career Development, Compensation, Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction.

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Introduction

Employee performance is widely recognized as a critical determinant of organizational effectiveness, as it serves as a primary indicator of an organization's success in achieving its strategic objectives and reflects the effectiveness of human resource management practices (Nduati & Wanyoike, 2022). In competitive service-oriented contexts, aligning human contributions with organizational strategy is essential to enhancing value-creating outcomes, as individual work outcomes are viewed through systems that promote strategic alignment between personnel inputs and service quality (Tavares & Vaz, 2025). Employee competence and performance play a critical role in organizational effectiveness within highly competitive and dynamic environments. Competent employees possess the capability to respond effectively to environmental challenges while improving productivity. These attributes enable organizations to sustain competitiveness and adapt to continuous change (Wijayanti & Sari, 2023).

State-owned organizations operating in professional service sectors face elevated expectations regarding service precision, reliability, and institutional accountability. These demands intensify the strategic importance of employee performance, as service outcomes are closely scrutinized and directly reflect organizational integrity and public trust. Organizations engaged in inspection, testing, and certification services rely heavily on employees' technical competence and consistency, as service outputs are directly assessed by clients, regulators, and other key stakeholders. Evidence from internal performance assessments indicates that overall employee performance has generally achieved expected organizational standards, suggesting operational effectiveness in meeting service targets. Human resource management practices influence organizational performance through both direct and mediated processes, indicating that sustaining employee performance requires attention to internal organizational dynamics that shape employees' attitudes and work experiences. Moreover, sustainable employee performance is influenced by a combination of organizational practices, employee engagement, training, and motivational factors, highlighting the importance of understanding internal organizational contexts beyond performance outcomes alone (Hendri, 2025; Rotea et al., 2023).

Despite the generally positive performance outcomes, internal assessments reveal notable human resource challenges related to compensation and career development that may affect employees' job satisfaction. Survey results indicate that employees perceive compensation practices as insufficiently aligned with workload, responsibility, and performance contributions, leading to concerns regarding fairness and adequacy of rewards. In addition, limited clarity and perceived inequality in career development opportunities have emerged as sources of dissatisfaction, particularly regarding promotion pathways and professional growth prospects. These conditions suggest that human resource development practices, including compensation, career development, and related organizational support, significantly impact employee performance through job satisfaction, indicating that addressing underlying HR factors is essential for sustaining employee performance beyond achieving performance (Keltu, 2024).

Career development is frequently emphasized as a strategic mechanism for improving employee performance; however, existing empirical studies have produced inconsistent

results regarding this relationship. Some research suggests that opportunities for career advancement and skill development contribute positively to employee performance (Keltu, 2024; Pham et al., 2024), whereas other studies find limited or insignificant effects (Rahayu et al., 2026). This divergence in findings indicates that the role of career development in shaping employee performance may not be uniform and is likely influenced by contextual conditions such as organizational career management practices, workforce characteristics, and the alignment of career opportunities with employee expectations. The absence of consistent empirical evidence points to an unresolved gap in understanding the conditions under which career development effectively enhances employee performance. Consequently, further investigation is necessary to provide clearer insights into this relationship across different organizational settings.

Compensation is often positioned as a strategic tool for enhancing employee performance; however, empirical findings addressing this relationship have yet to reach a clear consensus. While some studies demonstrate that well-designed compensation systems are associated with higher levels of employee performance (Fachiroh & Suratman, 2023; Saban et al., 2020), other research reports minimal or insignificant effects (Panjaitan & Sinaga, 2022). This variation suggests that the effectiveness of compensation in driving employee performance may depend on situational factors, including how compensation is structured, the criteria used to assess performance, and broader organizational policies. The absence of consistent evidence points to an unresolved gap in the literature concerning the conditions under which compensation contributes meaningfully to employee performance. Accordingly, further investigation is necessary to refine understanding of this relationship across diverse organizational contexts.

While career development is commonly viewed as a key organizational practice that contributes to employees' job satisfaction, empirical evidence addressing this relationship remains inconclusive. Some studies demonstrate that well-structured career development opportunities enhance job satisfaction (Darmadi & Suwanto, 2025; Kurniawanto et al., 2025), whereas other research reports limited or insignificant effects (Reners et al., 2024). The variation in these findings suggests that the impact of career development on job satisfaction may depend on contextual factors such as organizational policies, career management systems, and individual career expectations. This lack of consistent evidence highlights the need for further investigation to better understand how and under what conditions career development influences job satisfaction across different organizational contexts.

Although compensation has long been considered a fundamental factor influencing employees' job satisfaction, empirical findings on this relationship remain inconclusive. Several studies suggest that fair and competitive compensation enhances job satisfaction (Saputra & Rijanti, 2025; Zayed et al., 2022) while other studies report weak or nonsignificant effects (Rosalia et al., 2020), indicating that compensation alone may not be sufficient to ensure higher levels of job satisfaction. These divergent findings imply that the relationship between compensation and job satisfaction is context-dependent and may vary according to organizational compensation systems, employee expectations, and labor market conditions. Consequently, further research is required to clarify this

relationship and to re-examine the role of compensation in shaping job satisfaction across different organizational contexts.

Although job satisfaction has been widely examined as an important determinant of employee performance, existing empirical findings remain inconsistent. Several studies find that job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance (Afuan et al., 2024; Pham et al., 2024), while other studies report weak or nonsignificant relationships (Panjaitan & Sinaga, 2022). These divergent results suggest that the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance is not yet fully understood and may vary across organizational contexts. Therefore, further research is needed to clarify this relationship and to re-examine the role of job satisfaction in explaining variations in employee performance across different organizational settings.

Based on the identified research gap and preliminary data, this study aims to examine the effects of compensation and career development on employee performance, with job satisfaction serving as a mediating variable. The study is conducted at PT Sucofindo (Persero) Branch Banjarmasin, a state-owned enterprise operating in the inspection, testing, and certification sector, where employee performance is critical to ensuring service quality, regulatory compliance, and organizational credibility. This study contributes to the literature by clarifying the psychological mechanism through which compensation and career development influence employee performance in a state-owned professional service context. By positioning job satisfaction as a mediating variable, the study extends prior research that has predominantly examined direct relationships and offers a more nuanced explanation of performance sustainability in highly regulated service organizations. This study adopts a focused examination of the organizational context to generate empirical evidence on the role of human resource practices in shaping employee performance through job satisfaction within a highly regulated professional service environment. The findings are expected to extend the human resource management and employee performance literature, particularly in the context of state-owned service organizations

Literature Review

Two-factor Theory

Herzberg (2003) proposed that the factors generating job satisfaction are conceptually distinct from those leading to job dissatisfaction. Motivator factors such as achievement, recognition, responsibility, work itself, and opportunities for growth and advancement are intrinsic to the job and contribute to the development of internal motivation and enhanced performance. In contrast, hygiene factors including company policy, supervision, working conditions, interpersonal relationships, job security, and salary primarily function to prevent dissatisfaction rather than to create sustained motivation. From this perspective, job satisfaction is largely associated with the presence of motivator factors, whereas dissatisfaction tends to arise when hygiene factors are inadequately addressed. Accordingly, organizations should not only ensure adequate foundational conditions but also design jobs that foster achievement and development, as satisfaction derived from intrinsic aspects of work can support sustained employee performance.

Goal-Setting Theory

Locke & Latham (2002) explain that specific and challenging goals improve performance because they focus attention, increase effort, and strengthen persistence in completing tasks. These effects become stronger when individuals are committed to their goals and believe that achieving them will lead to meaningful and fair outcomes. Pursuing demanding goals also promotes continuous learning and the development of more effective work strategies, supporting both performance and skill growth. When achievements are followed by appropriate rewards and visible opportunities for advancement, individuals tend to feel proud and more satisfied with their work. In this way, satisfaction derived from goal attainment acts as an important link between rewards, career development, and sustained employee performance.

Compensation and Employee Performance

Compensation encompasses both financial and non-financial rewards provided by organizations as recognition of employees' contributions and achievements. Adequate and fair compensation acts as an important driver of employee performance because it motivates employees to work more effectively and align their efforts with organizational targets. Vroom (1964) explains that employees are more likely to enhance their performance when they believe that increased effort will lead to desirable rewards. Empirical evidence indicates that appropriate compensation levels can enhance performance by strengthening work commitment and productivity (Fachiroh & Suratman, 2023). In addition to direct financial rewards, recognition programs and performance bonuses play an essential role in acknowledging outstanding achievements and reinforcing positive work behavior. Studies across various sectors also confirm that performance-based incentives significantly improve employee output and overall performance (Pham et al., 2024).

H₁: Compensation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

Career Development and Employee Performance

Career development represents organizational efforts to improve employees' competencies through promotion, job rotation, training, and further education. Such initiatives enable employees to enhance their technical and managerial skills, which contribute to better work outcomes. Career development is closely associated with improved employee performance, since opportunities for training and advancement enable employees to strengthen their competencies and perform their tasks more effectively (Saputra & Rijanti, 2025). Well-implemented development programs also ensure that employees possess the competencies required to meet job demands and exceed performance standards. Conversely, inadequate competence may limit employees' ability to perform optimally and increase the risk of substandard results (Panjaitan & Sinaga, 2022).

H₂: Career Development has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance

Compensation and Job Satisfaction

Compensation refers to all forms of financial and non-financial rewards received by employees in return for their work and contributions, including salaries, incentives, benefits, and recognition. Appropriate and fair compensation reflects the value of employees' efforts and plays an important role in shaping their motivation, morale, and overall job satisfaction. Compensation systems that are properly designed can enhance employees' happiness at work, strengthen organizational commitment, and positively influence work attitudes, thereby increasing job satisfaction (Idris et al., 2020). From a motivational perspective, compensation functions as a hygiene and motivational factor that reduces dissatisfaction and supports positive employee behavior, with employee motivation playing a mediating role in the relationship between compensation and job satisfaction (Zayed et al., 2022). Furthermore, employees' satisfaction with pay and benefits is closely associated with their overall job satisfaction, particularly in labor-intensive and context-specific industries, indicating that compensation remains a critical determinant of job satisfaction across different organizational settings (Ullah et al., 2024).

H3: Compensation has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction.

Career Development and job satisfaction

Career development is a continuous process that aligns individual career planning with organizational career management to support long-term employee growth and fulfillment. Through training, education, mentoring, and structured career planning, employees gain opportunities to enhance their skills and prepare for future responsibilities. Empirical evidence suggests that well-organized development programs increase employees' awareness of their career potential and readiness, thereby improving job satisfaction (Kurniawanto et al., 2025). Poorly communicated or unstructured career development programs can make employees feel stuck in their roles and gradually lower their level of job satisfaction (Darmadi & Suwanto, 2025). On the other hand, development opportunities that align with employees' career expectations can serve as a strong source of motivation and contribute positively to their overall job satisfaction (Robianto et al., 2020).

H4: Career Development has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction.

Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Job satisfaction describes a positive emotional state resulting from the evaluation of one's work experience, including satisfaction with the work itself, salary, recognition, supervision, coworker relationships, and advancement opportunities (Saban et al., 2020). Spector (1997) argues that employees who experience higher levels of job satisfaction tend to exhibit more positive work behaviors, including increased effort and performance. Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in enhancing employee performance, as satisfied employees tend to exhibit higher motivation, commitment, and effectiveness in carrying out their tasks. Higher levels of job satisfaction are often followed by improved employee performance, since satisfied employees are generally more engaged and effective in carrying out their tasks (Pham et al., 2024). Job satisfaction is also associated with

improvements in work quality, quantity, timeliness, task execution, and responsibility, indicating that greater satisfaction contributes to stronger performance outcomes (Afuan et al., 2024). This relationship is further supported by motivational perspectives such as Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, Equity Theory, and Job Characteristics Theory, which emphasize that supportive work environments and fair rewards foster both satisfaction and performance (Babu et al., 2025).

H₅: Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction helps explain how organizational practices shape employee performance. When compensation is fair and proportional, employees tend to develop more positive attitudes toward their work, which can lead to better performance outcomes (Fachiroh & Suratman, 2023). This pattern aligns with social exchange theory, suggesting that employees respond to favorable treatment, such as recognition and performance bonuses, with stronger commitment and improved performance (Pham et al., 2024). In the same way, career development initiatives including training, skill enhancement, promotion opportunities, and clear career paths contribute to performance not only directly but also indirectly by increasing job satisfaction (Saputra & Rijanti, 2025; Yuliastari & Darma, 2025). Employees who feel supported in their career growth are generally more engaged and more capable of meeting organizational expectations.

H₆: Job Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Compensation and Employee Performance.

H₇: Job Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Career Development and Employee Performance.

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Model

Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design to examine the relationships and causal effects among variables using numerical data. The approach is selected as the study focuses on measuring variables in a structured and

systematic manner and analyzing them using statistical techniques to produce generalizable conclusions. The research was conducted at PT Sucofindo (Persero) Banjarmasin Branch, involving all 134 employees as respondents. A non-probability sampling technique with a census (total sampling) approach was employed, in which all members of the population were included as the research sample.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire with a Likert scale and distributed online via Google Forms. Data analysis was conducted by describing respondents' characteristics and examining the relationships among variables using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). This method is suitable for analyzing simultaneous relationships among latent variables, encompassing both the measurement model and the structural model, and is appropriate for complex research models with non-normal data distributions. To address potential common method bias from single-source self-reported questionnaire data collected at one time point, full collinearity VIF analysis was conducted prior to PLS-SEM analysis.

All 134 participants provided informed consent before completing the online questionnaire via Google Forms. Participation was voluntary, with clear information about the study's purpose, confidentiality of responses (anonymous data collection), and the right to withdraw at any time without consequences.

Results and Discussion

Results

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Category	Items	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	109	81%
	Female	25	19%
Marital Status	Married	112	84%
	Unmarried	22	16%
Age	Less than 25 years old	4	3%
	26-35 years old	61	46%
	36-45 years old	48	36%
	More than 45 years old	21	16%
Education	High school or equivalent	15	11%
	Diploma	30	22%
	Bachelor's Degree	83	62%
	Master's Degree	6	4%
Tenure	0-10 years	70	52%
	11-15 years	30	22%
	16-20 years	21	16%
	More than 20 years	13	10%
Position	Functional	121	90%
	Structural	13	10%

Outer Model

Table 2. Loading Factor Convergent Validity

Variable (s)	Items	Loading Factor
Employee Performance	EP10	0.844
	EP11	0.840
	EP12	0.828
	EP13	0.841
	EP14	0.807
	EP16	0.774
	EP17	0.765
	EP18	0.771
	EP19	0.781
	EP2	0.710
	EP20	0.852
	EP21	0.857
	EP22	0.808
	EP23	0.758
	EP3	0.762
	EP4	0.774
	EP6	0.834
	EP7	0.808
	EP8	0.799
EP9	0.824	
Compensation	C2	0.808
	C3	0.859
	C4	0.800
	C5	0.789
	C6	0.771
Career Development	CD1	0.770
	CD10	0.765
	CD11	0.790
	CD12	0.736
	CD13	0.865
	CD14	0.821
	CD15	0.741
	CD2	0.766
CD3	0.796	
Job Satisfaction	JS4	0.726
	JS5	0.726
	JS6	0.860
	JS7	0.844
	JS8	0.841

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

Variable (s)	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Employee Performance	0.971	0.973	0.644
Compensation	0.865	0.902	0.650
Career Development	0.922	0.935	0.615
Job Satisfaction	0.859	0.899	0.643

Table 4. HTMT Value

	C	CD	EP	JS
C				
CD	0.777			
EP	0.617	0.693		
JS	0.851	0.869	0.770	

Table 5. Collinearity VIF Values

Relationship	VIF
Compensation → Employee Performance	2.406
Compensation → Job Satisfaction	1.978
Career Development → Employee Performance	2.889
Career Development → Job Satisfaction	1.978
Job Satisfaction → Employee Performance	3.218

All constructs meet the measurement model evaluation criteria. Loading factor (LF) > 0.70, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.50, Heterotrait–Monotrait ratio (HTMT) < 0.90, Composite Reliability (CR) > 0.70. Cronbach's alpha (α) ≥ 0.70. Convergent validity, discriminant validity, and internal consistency reliability are satisfied. The measurement model is suitable for subsequent structural model analysis (Hair et al., 2021). In addition, all VIF values are < 3.3, indicating that the research model does not exhibit common method bias.

Inner Model

Table 6. Effect Size (f^2) Determination Results

Relationship	f-square
Compensation → Employee Performance	0.002
Compensation → Job Satisfaction	0.216
Career Development → Employee Performance	0.047
Career Development → Job Satisfaction	0.461
Job Satisfaction → Employee Performance	0.153

The effect size analysis indicates that the Compensation contributes a relatively limited explanatory influence on Employee Performance, as reflected by an f^2 value of 0.002. Similarly, Career Development shows a weak contribution to Employee Performance with an f^2 value of 0.047. However, both the Compensation and Career Development display stronger influences on Job Satisfaction, with f^2 values of 0.216 and 0.461, respectively. Furthermore, Job Satisfaction display more substantial influence on Employee Performance, evidenced by an f^2 value of 0.153. This result suggests that Job Satisfaction plays a more prominent role in explaining variations in performance outcomes within the proposed model.

Table 7. Construct Cross-Validated Redundancy

Variable (s)	Q^2
Compensation (X1)	0.000
Career Development (X2)	0.000
Employee Performance (Y)	0.329
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.431

The Q^2 values indicate that Employee Performance (Y) and Job Satisfaction (Z) exceed zero, with values of 0.329 and 0.431, respectively, demonstrating that the model exhibits strong predictive relevance for both endogenous variables. The Q^2 values for Compensation (X1) and Career Development (X2) are equal to zero, confirming their roles as exogenous constructs within the model. Overall, these results indicate that the structural model possesses adequate predictive capability (Hair et al., 2021).

Table 8. R-Square Determination Coefficient Results

Variable (s)	R^2
Employee Performance (Y)	0.521
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.685

The R-square values indicate that Employee Performance (Y) has an R^2 of 0.521, suggesting that 52.1% of the variance in employee performance is explained by the independent variables included in the model. Job Satisfaction (Z) records an R^2 of 0.685, indicating that 68.5% of the variance in job satisfaction is accounted for by the predictor constructs employed.

Table 9. Goodness of Fit Value

Average AVE	Average R Square	Gof Value
0.638	0.611	0.624

The Goodness of Fit (GoF) value obtained is 0.624, calculated based on the average variance extracted (AVE) and the average R-square values, indicating a high level of model fit. This result suggests that the overall model adequately represents the

relationships between latent constructs and their indicators, supporting its suitability for explaining the phenomenon under investigation

Hypothesis Results

Table 10. Hypothesis Results

Variable (s) Relationship	P-Value	Path Coefficients	T-Statistics	Description
Compensation (X1) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.695	0.042	0.392	Rejected
Career Development (X2) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.009	0.252	2.608	Accepted
Compensation (X1) → Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.001	0.365	3.297	Accepted
Career Development (X2) → Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.000	0.532	5.090	Accepted
Job Satisfaction (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.000	0.480	4.562	Accepted
Compensation (X1) → Job Satisfaction (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.007	0.175	2.716	Accepted
Career Development (X2) → Job Satisfaction (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.002	0.256	3.131	Accepted

The results indicate that Compensation (X1) does not have a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y) ($p = 0.695$), leading to the rejection of the proposed hypothesis. Career Development (X2) demonstrates a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y) ($p = 0.009$), confirming the role of career development in enhancing employee performance. Compensation (X1) and Career Development (X2) both exert significant effects on Job Satisfaction (Z) ($p < 0.05$). Job Satisfaction (Z) also shows a significant influence on Employee Performance (Y) ($p < 0.05$). Indirect effect analysis reveals that Job Satisfaction (Z) mediates the relationships between Compensation (X1), Career Development (X2), and Employee Performance (Y), positioning job satisfaction as the primary mechanism linking human resource practices to performance outcomes within the research model.

Discussion

The findings indicate that the relationship between compensation and employee performance at PT Sucofindo (Persero) Banjarmasin Branch is positive but not statistically significant. Compensation does not function as a direct driver of performance improvement, but rather serves to maintain work stability and prevent dissatisfaction. This role positions compensation as a maintenance factor rather than a trigger for behavioral change in performance. These results differ from those reported by Saban et al. (2020) and Idris et al. (2020), who identified a significant effect of compensation on performance, reflecting differences in organizational context and employee characteristics. This condition suggests that performance improvement is more effectively driven through deeper psychological and structural mechanisms.

The positive and significant influence of career development on employee performance suggests that organizational investment in structured advancement pathways directly strengthens employees' capabilities and drives superior work outcomes. Clarity

of career paths and consistency in implementation provide direction for career advancement, strengthening motivation, responsibility, and employee commitment. This orientation supports the achievement of more optimal and sustainable performance outcomes. These findings are consistent with Saputra & Rijanti (2025) as well as Panjaitan & Sinaga (2022), who identify career development as a strategic determinant of employee performance.

The significant positive effect of compensation on job satisfaction suggests that adequate and equitable reward systems function as essential hygiene factors that prevent dissatisfaction and foster more favorable work attitudes. Job satisfaction increases when compensation is perceived as aligned with workload and job responsibilities. The role of compensation is more prominent in shaping work attitudes than in directly stimulating performance. This function reinforces compensation as a foundation for perceived fairness, job security, and acceptable working conditions. These findings are consistent with those of Fachiroh & Suratman (2023) and Afuan et al. (2024) who emphasize the significance of compensation in enhancing job satisfaction.

The significant positive influence of career development on job satisfaction indicates that advancement and growth opportunities function as intrinsic motivators that enhance employees' sense of achievement and overall job satisfaction. Clear promotion opportunities and sustainable development practices strengthen perceptions of fairness and organizational recognition. These conditions foster positive work attitudes and enhance employee job satisfaction. These findings align with Robianto et al. (2020) as well as Kurniawanto et al. (2025), who highlight the role of career development in improving job satisfaction through clear prospects.

The significant positive influence of job satisfaction on employee performance suggests that favorable work attitudes function as a psychological driver that enhances employees' motivation and behavioral engagement, ultimately translating into superior performance outcomes. Positive evaluations of overall work experiences are reflected in higher levels of motivation, engagement, and performance consistency. Job satisfaction functions as a mechanism that translates organizational policies into productive work behavior. These findings are consistent with Saban et al. (2020), who position job satisfaction as a key determinant of employee performance.

The significant indirect effect demonstrates that compensation influences employee performance through job satisfaction, suggesting that financial rewards first foster positive work attitudes, which subsequently drive improved performance outcomes. Compensation shapes perceptions of fairness and recognition, which subsequently enhances job satisfaction and encourages productive work behavior. Without job satisfaction, compensation tends to remain an administrative fulfillment without a tangible impact on performance. These findings align with Robianto et al. (2020) who emphasize the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between compensation and performance.

Career development also exerts an indirect influence on employee performance through job satisfaction, indicating that structured growth opportunities enhance performance not only by strengthening competencies but also by fostering positive work

attitudes that translate into higher task effectiveness. Certainty regarding career direction shapes job satisfaction through perceptions of advancement opportunities and organizational recognition. Job satisfaction subsequently enhances employee engagement and performance orientation. These findings are consistent with Kurniawanto et al. (2025), who identifies job satisfaction as the primary mediator in the relationship between career development and employee performance.

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. Data were collected from a single branch of PT Sucofindo (Persero) Banjarmasin, limiting generalizability to other branches, industries, or regions.

Conclusion

Compensation does not exert a significant direct effect on employee performance, despite exhibiting a positive direction, indicating that compensation primarily functions to maintain work stability rather than to directly enhance performance. Career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, underscoring the importance of clear career structures and consistent implementation in strengthening responsibility and performance orientation. Compensation and career development both significantly influence job satisfaction, confirming their role in shaping positive work evaluations. Job satisfaction, in turn, has a significant effect on employee performance and operates as a key explanatory mechanism. Indirect effect analysis demonstrates that job satisfaction mediates the effects of compensation and career development on employee performance. These findings indicate that performance improvement in state-owned professional service organizations depends on integrated human resource practices that emphasize job satisfaction alongside compensation and career development. Future research is encouraged to incorporate additional variables such as leadership, organizational culture, organizational commitment, and workload or job stress to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of employee performance.

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